

Strategy

Search term groups:

osteoblasts – osteoblast precursors – osteoclasts – osteoclast precursors – bone related words – co-culture related words

Search steps

Include studies mentioning osteoblasts OR osteoblast precursors in combination with bone related words
AND

Include studies mentioning osteoclasts OR osteoclast precursors in combination with bone related words
AND

include studies mentioning co-cultures

EMBASE

Osteoblast

exp osteoblast/ OR exp osteoblast cell line/ OR Osteoblast*.ti,ab,kw. OR Pre-osteoblast*.ti,ab,kw. OR preosteoblast.ti,ab,kw. OR osteoprogenitor*.ti,ab,kw. OR ((Bone forming OR osteogenic) AND cells).ti,ab,kw. OR (osteogen* AND cell*).ti,ab,kw.

Osteoblast progenitor

exp mesenchymal stem cell/ OR Mesenchymal stem.ti,ab,kw. OR Mesenchymal stromal.ti,ab,kw. OR Mesenchymal progenitor.ti,ab,kw. OR bone marrow stem.ti,ab,kw. OR Bone marrow stromal.ti,ab,kw. OR MSC*.ti,ab,kw. OR Multipotent stem.ti,ab,kw. OR Multipotent stromal.ti,ab,kw. OR Multi-potent stem.ti,ab,kw. OR Multi-potent stromal.ti,ab,kw. OR Stromal cell*.ti,ab,kw. OR Stromal fraction.ti,ab,kw. OR Adipose derived stem.ti,ab,kw. OR Adipose derived stromal.ti,ab,kw. OR Adipose stem.ti,ab,kw. OR Adipose stromal.ti,ab,kw. OR Fat derived stem.ti,ab,kw. OR Fat derived stromal.ti,ab,kw. OR MC3T3*.ti,ab,kw. OR Periodontal ligament cell*.ti,ab,kw. OR MLO-Y4.ti,ab,kw. OR MLO Y4.ti,ab,kw. OR MLO A5.ti,ab,kw. OR MLO-A5.ti,ab,kw.

Bone related

exp bone/ OR exp osteolysis/ OR exp bone development/ OR exp osteoporosis/ OR exp osteopetrosis/ OR bone formation.ti,ab,kw. OR Resorption.ti,ab,kw. OR resorbing.ti,ab,kw. OR Bone remodeling.ti,ab,kw. OR bone remodelling.ti,ab,kw. OR Bone re-modeling.ti,ab,kw. OR bone re-modelling.ti,ab,kw. OR (Mineral* AND matrix AND deposit*).ti,ab,kw. OR Resorpt*.ti,ab,kw. OR Osteoporosis.ti,ab,kw. OR osteoporotic.ti,ab,kw. OR osteopetrosis.ti,ab,kw. OR osteopetrotic.ti,ab,kw. OR bone diseas*.ti,ab,kw.

Osteoclast

exp osteoclast activity/ or exp osteoclast/ or exp bone marrow osteoclast cell/ OR osteoclast*.ti,ab,kw. OR pre-osteoclast*.ti,ab,kw. OR preosteoclast*.ti,ab,kw. OR resorbing cells.ti,ab,kw. OR odontoclast*.ti,ab,kw. OR cementoclast*.ti,ab,kw.

Osteoclast precursors

exp monocyte/ OR exp hematopoietic stem cell/ OR exp monocyte macrophage precursor cell/ OR monocy*.ti,ab,kw. OR monoblast*.ti,ab,kw. OR promonocy*.ti,ab,kw. OR THP*.ti,ab,kw. OR RAW264*.ti,ab,kw. OR RAW 264*.ti,ab,kw. OR RAW-264*.ti,ab,kw. OR Mononuclear cell*.ti,ab,kw.

OR Mononuclear fraction.ti,ab,kw. OR ((Hematopoietic OR haematopoietic) AND (stem OR stromal)).ti,ab,kw.

Co-culture

exp coculture/ OR exp organoid/ OR co-cult*.ti,ab,kw. OR cocult*.ti,ab,kw. OR coincubat*.ti,ab,kw. OR co-incubat*.ti,ab,kw. OR multi-cultur*.ti,ab,kw. OR multicultur*.ti,ab,kw. OR tri-cultur*.ti,ab,kw. OR tricultur*.ti,ab,kw. OR cultured together.ti,ab,kw. OR cultivated together.ti,ab,kw. OR Cell interaction*.ti,ab,kw. OR Two cell types.ti,ab,kw. OR (simultaneously AND (seeded OR cultured)).ti,ab,kw. OR Bone model.ti,ab,kw. OR Bone models.ti,ab,kw. OR (Coupling AND (bone OR formation OR resorption OR remodelling OR remodeling)).ti,ab,kw. OR Resorption model.ti,ab,kw. OR Model of resorption.ti,ab,kw. OR Mixed culture.ti,ab,kw. OR Synchronous cult*.ti,ab,kw. OR Simultaneous cult*.ti,ab,kw. OR binary cult*.ti,ab,kw. OR dual culture.ti,ab,kw. OR bi-cult*.ti,ab,kw. OR colocalization.ti,ab,kw. OR co-localization.ti,ab,kw. OR colocalisation.ti,ab,kw. OR co-localisation.ti,ab,kw. OR heterocult*.ti,ab,kw. OR heterotypic cult*.ti,ab,kw. OR organoid.ti,ab,kw. OR organotypic cult*.ti,ab,kw. OR Trans-well.ti,ab,kw. OR Transwell.ti,ab,kw. OR Permeable barrier.ti,ab,kw. OR Well insert.ti,ab,kw. OR Well inserts.ti,ab,kw. OR Well-insert.ti,ab,kw. OR Well-inserts.ti,ab,kw.